

The $[R_3S][HgI_3]$ family : contributions of P. C. Rây and some later developments

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Abstract : This article primarily concerns the history of the title family of salts which were correctly formulated in 1930 by Rây. Later structure determination of the $[Me_3S]^+$ salt revealed the presence of discrete $[HgI_3]^-$ anion which has become a model example of trigonal planar tricoordination in transition metal chemistry of simple ligands. The different structure of the $[Et_3S]^+$ salt and the possible nature of the species in solutions of $[R_3S][HgI_3]$ in polar solvents like acetone are briefly noted.

Keywords : Triiodomercury(II), trialkyl sulfonium salts, tricoordination.

Introduction

In leading text books of inorganic chemistry^{1,2} one example of the relatively rare phenomenon of tricoordination³ among transition metal complexes of simple ligands is almost invariably cited viz. the triiodomercury(II) anion as in the trimethyl sulfonium salt $[Me_3S][HgI_3]$ which is now known to incorporate trigonal planar $[HgI_3]^-$ and pyramidal $[Me_3S]^+$, as shown in **1**, in the crystalline state. It is hardly remembered that the above 1 : 1 electrolytic formulation of the salt was first suggested by P. C. Rây in 1930 although at that time there was no discussion of coordination number and geometry.

In this article we trace (i) the events that led Rây to the general family of trialkyl sulfonium salts, $[R_3S][HgI_3]$, of which the above salt is a particular example, (ii) the basis on which he proposed their formulation and (iii) later work by others on structure determination. The hundred and fifty second birth anniversary year of Rây is 2013 and we write this historical account as a tribute to him on this occasion.

The historical thread in four parts

(1) *Initial synthesis, structural proposal and solution conductivity :*

In his early research at Presidency College Rây's favourite metal to play with was mercury. In 1904 he succeeded⁴ in preparing pure mercuric nitrite, $Hg(NO_2)_2$, by reacting mercuric chloride with silver nitrite in aqueous media. Its reactions with different ligands generated a panorama of new systems some of which were explored by Rây and his students over a number of years. Since mercuric nitrite itself was rather unstable, often the easily prepared and stable double nitrite $Na_2[Hg(NO_2)_4]$ was conveniently used as starting material in these explorations. In 1916 Rây reported^{5,6} that the reaction of simple alkyl thiols of type RSH with sodium mercuric nitrite in solution afforded the crystalline thiolatomercuric nitrite complex $RSHgNO_2$ which was described by him as 'mercury mercaptide nitrite'. It represented a new family of thiolato complexes of mercury closely akin to the thiolatomercuric halides $RSHgX$ which were already known.

The reaction of this presumably polymeric⁷ complex with alkyl iodide (RI) afforded a mixture of nitroalkane and alkyl nitrite and a yellow crystalline solid to which he assigned the composition $[R_2S_2, HgI_2, RI]$ on the basis

of analytical data for mercury and iodine only. Regarding its constitution he drew analogy with the work of

Smiles⁸ who had proposed that the 1 : 1 adduct of dialkyl sulfide and mercuric iodide, $[\text{R}_2\text{S}, \text{HgI}_2]$, has the constitution **2** bearing tetravalent sulfur. Rây extended Smiles' hypothesis to dialkyl disulfide and proposed^{5,6} that in the presence of mercuric iodide and alkyl iodides "the two bivalent sulphur atoms of dialkyl disulphide become quadrivalent" as in the structure **3**.

The $[\text{R}_2\text{S}_2, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}]$ type compounds were insoluble in water but were generally soluble in acetone. In 1921 Rây found⁹ that the acetone solutions were fairly good electrical conductors indicating that the compounds are actually salts. The molecular conductivity was found to increase with dilution and its magnitude was similar to that observed for potassium iodide. He concluded that the compounds "... appear, therefore, to be true salts dissociating as uni-univalent electrolytes, possibly into a negative iodine ion and a complex positive ion containing the sulphur chain". He did not specify which iodine atom was to be designated as iodide ion.

(2) *A mistake and its correction :*

The next stage of development came in 1930 when Rây was able to detect an error in the given composition of the compounds and to visualize their true nature¹⁰. It all happened when he was exploring the reaction of alkyl sulfide or dialkyl disulfide with cadmium iodide and alkyl iodide. He found no trace of $[\text{R}_2\text{S}_2, \text{CdI}_2, \text{RI}]$ in the product which solely consisted of $[\text{R}_2\text{S}, \text{CdI}_2, \text{RI}]$ or $[2\text{R}_2\text{S}, \text{CdI}_2, \text{RI}]$ depending on conditions. This led him to reexamine the case of mercury carefully resulting in the conclusion that in his earlier works the compounds had been "mistakenly taken to be chain-compounds of the sulphonium type".

The composition $[\text{R}_2\text{S}_2, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}]$ was thus found to be in error, the true composition being $[\text{R}_2\text{S}, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}]$ which has one sulfur atom less than that in the original formulation. Rây could now prepare¹⁰ these by simpler methods.

For example the $\text{R}=\text{Me}$ compound was made from MeSH , MeI and HgI , as well as from Me_2S , MeI and HgI_2 or from Me_2S_2 , MeI and HgI or from preformed Me_3SI and HgI_2 . Always the same yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 163 °C, resulted and it was identical with the compound obtained from $[\text{Hg}(\text{SMe})(\text{NO}_2)]$ and MeI fourteen years earlier^{5,6}.

(3) *The final step :*

The $[\text{R}_2\text{S}, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}]$ type compounds had been reported by Smiles⁸ as early as 1900 as a product of the reaction among R_2S , RI and HgI_2 . The same product is formed¹¹ when R_2S_2 is used in place of R_2S but then iodine is a byproduct. Smiles suggested the constitution **4** based on hexavalent sulfur which he considered to be the "simplest

and most probable". An octahedral geometry for sulfur may have been tacitly implied by Smiles and this aspect was explicitly elaborated¹² in 1902 by Pope and Neville who even suggested the achiral meridional geometry **5** for the isolated compounds.

As seen earlier, the solution electrical conductivity data¹⁰ of the compounds, mistakenly formulated earlier as $[\text{R}_2\text{S}_2, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}]$, had indicated that they behave as uni-univalent electrolytes. With the corrected formulation $[\text{R}_2\text{S}, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}]$, this description remained valid as the molecular weight changed only slightly. This prompted Rây to abandon the hexavalent sulfur model of Smiles and to conclude¹⁰ that the $[\text{R}_2\text{S}, \text{HgI}_2, \text{RI}]$ species are actually 1 : 1 electrolytic trialkyl sulfonium salts of triiodomercury(II), $[\text{R}_3\text{S}][\text{HgI}_3]$. Subsequently Cavell and Sugden while reporting¹³ on the solution properties like electrical conductivity and parachor of the compounds fully upheld Rây's conclusion.

(4) *X-ray structure :*

The X-ray crystal structure of $[\text{Me}_3\text{S}][\text{HgI}_3]$ was solved¹⁴ in 1963 (a more detailed report¹⁵ appeared in 1966) and the authors wrote : "Rây and Adhikary decided from conductivity measurements that the structure is ionic

and this conclusion is confirmed by our results". A more refined structure was reported¹⁶ in 1995. Recently the structure has been determined¹⁷ at low temperature. The broad features of structure are the same in all the determinations. A plot of the structure of the $[HgI_3]^-$ anion in the last determination¹⁷ is shown in Fig. 1. It is nearly planar, the Hg atom being displaced by only 0.12 Å from the plane of the iodine atoms. The order of distances

Fig. 1. An ORTEP plot of the triiodomercury(II) anion in the trimethyl sulfonium salt.

follow the order : Hg-I3 < Hg-I2 < Hg-I1 (2.692(1), 2.723(1), 2.741(1) Å) and the angles are I1-Hg-I2, 110.75(3); I1-Hg-I3, 124.03(3) and I2-Hg-I3, 124.63(4). The trend of the distances as well as the relative smallness of one of the angles is believed to be a sequel to intermolecular interactions in the lattice¹⁷.

The X-ray structure of $[Et_3S][HgI_3]$ is also known¹⁶. Unlike the trimethyl salt it is dimeric, $[Et_3S]_2[Hg_2I_6]$ where the $[Hg_2I_6]^{2-}$ anion is iodide bridged and each mercury atom has a tetrahedral S_4 coordination sphere as depicted approximately in 6. Thus the formula $[R_3S][HgI_3]$ does

not necessarily define the mercuriiodide entity that is actually present in the crystal lattice. Indeed halide bridging in $[M(\text{halide})_3]^{n-}$ species making the tricoordinate description untenable is common place³.

Concluding comments

The $[R_3S][HgI_3]$ family was so formulated for the first time in January 1930 by Rây on the basis of solution

electrical conductivity data. The $[HgI_3]^-$ ion in the crystalline trimethyl sulfonium salt has turned out to be a model example of discrete tricoordination among $[M(\text{halide})_3]^{n-}$ species. In solutions in polar coordinating solvents the $[HgI_3]^-$ ion becomes¹⁶ tetrahedral due to solvent coordination. Thus it is very likely that the acetone solutions used by Rây in conductivity measurements had $[R_3S]^+$ and $[HgI_3(OCMe_2)]^-$ ions for every compound since acetone could cleave any iodide bridge present in the lattice. Every member of the $[R_3S][HgI_3]$ family could thus behave as a 1 : 1 electrolyte. These are not matters that chemists would normally consider in 1930 and coordination number and geometry were not issues of discussion in Rây's paper¹⁰.

References

1. F. A. Cotton, G. Wilkinson, X. A. Murillo and M. Bochmann, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 6th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc, New York, 1999, p. 4.
2. N. N. Greenwood and A. Earnshaw, "Chemistry of the Elements", 2nd ed., Butterworth-Heinemann, Oxford, 1997 (Printed in India 2005), p. 913.
3. P. G. Eller, D. C. Bradley, M. B. Hursthouse and D. W. Meek, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, **24**, 1.
4. P. C. Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 523.
5. P. C. Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **109**, 131.
6. P. C. Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **109**, 603.
7. A. J. Canty, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1981, **37A**, 283.
8. S. Smiles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, **77**, 160.
9. P. C. Rây and K. Kumar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 1643.
10. P. C. Rây and N. Adhikary, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 297.
11. T. P. Hilditch and S. Smiles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1394.
12. W. J. Pope and A. Neville, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, **81**, 1552.
13. H. J. Cavell and S. Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2572.
14. R. H. Fenn, J. W. H. Oldham and D. C. Phillips, *Nature*, 1963, **198**, 381.
15. R. H. Fenn, *Acta Cryst.*, 1966, **20**, 20.
16. L. A. Bengtsson, B. Norén and H. Stegemann, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1995, **49**, 391.
17. P. Ghosh and A. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2013, **52**, 0000.

